

A global perspective on trade in jaguar parts from South America

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Abstract

Starting in 2010 and accelerating in 2014, reports of trade and seizures of jaguar parts surfaced from several countries in South America. In this paper we summarize knowledge to date including official reports, peer-reviewed publications, public articles, seizure records, online searches, and market surveys in source countries in South America and big cat consuming countries in Asia. We found widespread records of domestic use and commerce in jaguar parts, in many cases without effective enforcement of existing laws to provide a substantial deterrent. We found less abundant solid records of trade from South America to China, with the exception of Bolivia where 95.4% of the historic interceptions of jaguar canines were oriented towards China, and Suriname where seizures in airports testify to international trade. International trade is particularly onerous as it can drive domestic killing of jaguars at an increased level due to higher prices and diversified markets. More material may be shipped to Asian markets than we have detected and we recommend vigilance in all potential mediums for transport (passenger aircraft, air freight, postal services, courier services, and marine shipping). We present a summarized review of relevant legal structures. The depth and breadth of domestic commerce that we recorded from diverse sources suggest the need for increased enforcement of existing

52 laws, coupled with behavior change and livelihood alternatives. All jaguar killing starts at the
53 local level, and when there is a local national market for jaguar parts there is less incentive to
54 pursue the means and methods for coexistence already tested and proven in much of the species'
55 range.
56

57 **Introduction**

58
59 The jaguar (*Panthera onca*), known for its golden rosetted coat and cultural symbolism, has been
60 considered a valuable and sought-after species throughout the history of Latin American
61 societies. Archaeological records show that jaguar body parts travelled long distances across the
62 Caribbean Sea, potentially transported as prized items of exchange between Amerindian and
63 Caribbean societies, as early as the Ceramic Age (500 BC to AD 1500) (Laffoon et al. 2014).
64 During the 18th century, there are records of approximately 2,000 jaguars being exported
65 annually from Buenos Aires to Europe for the fur industry (Swank & Teer 1989). Jaguar trade
66 reached unprecedented commercial levels during the first three-quarters of the 20th century,
67 when the spotted cat fashion trend reached its peak. In Brazil, an estimated 180,000 jaguars were
68 killed during this period (Antunes et al. 2016), causing a widespread population decline. In
69 response to the imminent extinction risk posed to jaguars and other spotted cats by the fur trade,
70 in 1975, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora
71 (CITES) listed these species under Appendix I, prohibiting their commercial trade across
72 international boundaries (CITES 2017, Reuter et al. 2018).

73
74 Even though by the end of the 20th century, international jaguar trade was virtually over, low-
75 scale but widespread jaguar trading continued to occur domestically, commonly as a by-product
76 of killing caused by opportunistic encounters between people and jaguars or human-jaguar
77 conflict, as well as for subsistence and cultural use (Arias & Lambert 2019, Arias et al. 2020,
78 2021a). However, starting in 2010, reports of trade and seizures of jaguar body parts surfaced
79 from several countries across the jaguar range, suggesting a re-emergence of international jaguar
80 trade (Kernam 2010, Nuñez & Aliaga-Rossel 2016). Between 2014 and November 2023, 825
81 jaguar canines have been seized in trafficking cases linked to Chinese individuals in Bolivia and
82 in mainland China. Other similar cases were registered in the region, including the sale of jaguar
83 body parts in physical and online markets, and the preparation of jaguar paste in Suriname for
84 alleged export to China (Lemieux & Bruschi 2019, Verheij 2019, SERFOR & WCS 2020).
85 These seizures and reports mobilized attention on the issue. Subsequent reports and publications
86 have shed light on the drivers and dynamics of the trade (e.g., Morcatty et al. 2020). This team of
87 international experts explored the state of the evidence on this threat in 2023, focusing on its
88 geographical characteristics and nuances. The paper starts with preliminary results of a seven-
89 language investigation of online trade in jaguar parts, transitions into specific country analyses
90 and legal considerations, and closes with recommendations for future actions.

91 92 **Online investigations of jaguar trade conducted 2019-2020**

93
94 Between May 2019 and March 2020, a multi-national team of researchers conducted systematic
95 searches for online trade of jaguar parts in seven languages (Spanish, Portuguese, Vietnamese,
96 Chinese, French, Dutch, English) (Polisar et al.2023). The team searched for offers of sale of
97 jaguar parts and processed items, as advertised, through multiple platforms, accessible via search

98 engines, online marketplaces, video-sharing, social media and weblogs (blogs). The results were
99 collated in a standardized database including the platforms, assessed country locations of posts,
100 jaguar part and product type, prices and other trade information where available, and
101 corresponding images of jaguar parts and products were visually reviewed, where available.
102 Platforms showing jaguar parts varied across countries and languages. Methods such as
103 standardized collection and metrics of effort facilitated structured searches, subsequent analyses
104 and interpretations and revealed the most productive search engines and platforms for potential
105 future searches. Following data collection, experts from Noel Kempff Mercado Natural History
106 Museum in Bolivia with expertise identifying and classifying jaguar parts resulting from a
107 successful prosecution of a jaguar trafficking case in Santa Cruz visually verified images as
108 jaguar. The analyses presented here incorporate the results of image review, yet should be still
109 considered preliminary.

110
111 Raw results included a total of 230 posts motivated by trade in jaguar parts; other posts referred
112 to sharing news about jaguars, or posting images of parts but with an unclear motivation, or
113 wearing items, and these were not included. From the 230 posts, 71 posts contained images that
114 were identified as definitely jaguar. We sampled a ten-year period and found that the numbers of
115 posts increased over time from 2009 to 2019, which may be an artifact of posts removed or
116 becoming moribund with time, or an increase in trade. Excluding duplicate posts, posts were
117 present on 31 distinct platforms, and the posts with images verified as jaguar were present on 12
118 platforms, comprised of 10 online marketplace sites (18 posts or 25.4% posts) and 2 social
119 network sites (53 posts or 74.6% posts).

120
121 The most widely used language in posts was Spanish. In our searches 98.6% of all posts
122 accompanied by verified jaguar images were in Spanish, Chinese, and Portuguese. Whilst
123 Vietnamese language searches identified 31 posts without duplicates, none of the posts
124 accompanied by an image were deemed to be jaguar.

125
126 The location was assessed by researchers for 193 of all posts, with records from at least 17
127 countries (plus one subset indicating posts derived from one of two countries, but unclear
128 which), however, only 64 posts from at least 9 countries included images that were definitely
129 jaguar, the most prolific being Brazil, Mexico and Bolivia. For the 437 parts that were counted in
130 posts, 15 categories of body parts were recorded, with teeth being the most popular item traded
131 (156 posts totalling 367 teeth), followed by skins, entire or fragments (37 skins, 1 skin piece and
132 1 skin scrap spanning at least seven countries), claws (12 posts of 14 claws), heads (nine posts
133 counting nine heads) and additional posts related to parts including bones, bodies and live
134 animals. Where the probable country of the post could be assessed (through platform addresses,
135 stated business geo-tag and other contextual information, but not physically verified by
136 researchers), jaguar skin posts were confined to jaguar range countries, with highest prevalence
137 in Brazil, Peru, Bolivia, and Mexico. Meanwhile, posts advertising teeth were most prevalent in
138 countries including Brazil, Mexico, Bolivia, China and Vietnam. However, following image
139 verification, those proportions changed with Mexican posts representing over one quarter of all
140 teeth counted (26.8%), Chinese posts one quarter of teeth (25.4%), Bolivia around one-fifth
141 (16.9%) and Brazil approximately one-tenth (12.7%). Vietnamese posts included tiger, leopard,
142 and bear teeth in posts obtained from searches targeting jaguar, illustrating some of the
143 challenges of search terms across geographies and languages, even with native speakers

144 conducting the research. Whilst searching in Chinese, and less intensively in Dutch, we
145 encountered very few records of medicinal oil/paste, a product reported from Suriname (Kerman
146 2010, Lemieux and Bruschi 2019, and World Animal Protection 2018).

147

148 **Bolivia National/International Trade - from reports/records 2014-2022**

149

150 The recent international trade in jaguar parts, especially canine teeth, was first reported in
151 Bolivia in July 2014, when Bolivian scientists who were camera trapping for jaguars in Madidi
152 National Park heard local radio advertisements offering to buy jaguar teeth in the nearby Beni
153 Department. This was immediately reported to the Ministry of the Environment and Water,
154 which coordinated with multiple authorities, including the Bolivian postal system, resulting in
155 the detection of several packages containing jaguar teeth, addressed to locations in China.
156 Simultaneously, customs officials stopped two individuals in El Alto International Airport in La
157 Paz travelling to China with jaguar teeth. Subsequently, three high profile legal cases of jaguar
158 teeth trafficking involving individuals of Chinese descent recently naturalized in Bolivia, further
159 increased national and international attention towards the threat of jaguar teeth trade (WCS,
160 WWF & Panthera 2016, Bale 2018, Franco 2018, León 2018), and led to increased investigations
161 on the matter, including academic and journalistic efforts, NGO investigations, and enforcement
162 operations in Bolivia (Nuñez & Aliaga-Rossel 2016, Verheij 2019, Arias et al. 2021a,b, CITES
163 2021, Earth League International 2021).

164

165 Efforts by the Wildlife Conservation Society to systematize official data on illegal wildlife trade
166 in Bolivia now include data provided by 62 institutions, including the Ministry of the
167 Environment and Water, the Bolivian Forestry and Environment Police (POFOMA) and most of
168 the Departmental governments and wildlife rescue centers in the country, and reveal that since
169 mid-2014 there are a total of 83 verifiable jaguar trafficking cases in Bolivia, with two additional
170 cases of jaguar parts seizures in China coming from Bolivia. Of these, 32 cases (37.6%) are of
171 jaguar teeth, amounting to 825 jaguar canines, making teeth the most trafficked part.
172 Additionally, 27 of the 83 cases so far, and 95,4% of Bolivian seized canines, are directly linked
173 to China. Online analyses in Bolivia have revealed 24 additional posts mainly on social media,
174 across the Bolivian lowlands. Although most recent cases of jaguar parts trafficking in Bolivia
175 occurred between 2014 and 2019, two cases were reported in 2022 and 3 cases in 2023, all
176 involving jaguar teeth. One of these involved 4 men of Chinese descent.

177

178 Previously, jaguar populations were recovering in protected areas in Bolivia (Mongabay 2018),
179 with indigenous territories (Polisar 2021), forestry concessions (Polisar et al. 2017), and cattle
180 ranches (Polisar 2021, Polisar et al. 2022), all demonstrating real potential for the conservation
181 of jaguar populations. However, conflicts between jaguars and livestock owners are likely to be
182 fueling part of the supply of jaguar teeth, responding to the high prices being paid for jaguar
183 canines, teeth, heads, claws and skins. Similarly, local people's attitudes towards jaguars are
184 mixed, with some indigenous groups publicly declaring to be against the illegal wildlife trade
185 and in favor of jaguars (CIPTA 2019, CRTM 2019), whilst other local actors have admitted their
186 fear of jaguars and willingness to kill them (Knox et al. 2019; Arias et al. 2021a). Aside from
187 cattle ranching, other forest dependent livelihoods (e.g., wild meat hunting, farming, non-timber
188 forest product collection) have been associated with jaguar killing (Arias et al. 2021a).
189 Moreover, a high proportion of rural households in north Bolivia buy, sell and use jaguar body

190 parts for a wide range of purposes, from decorative (jewelry, accessories, furnishings) to
191 medicinal (Arias et al. 2021b). Although illegal, these traditional uses continue in the Beni
192 Department, where it was shown recently that inmates of the Trinidad prison buy wildlife skins
193 to make wallets, bags and belts (Elwin et al. 2023). These handicrafts are commonly sold to
194 tourists in town markets, but are also bought in bulk by foreign middlemen for export. Four cases
195 of wildlife parts seized in La Paz, Santa Cruz, and Riberalta, with support from the Noel Kempff
196 Mercado Natural History Museum for forensic identification during 2022-2023, included jaguar
197 teeth or skin pieces. Illegal trade in jaguar teeth, alongside habitat loss and recent increases in
198 frequency and intensity of Amazonian fires, are currently the largest threats to jaguar populations
199 in Bolivia (Romero-Muñoz et al. 2019).

200

201 **Suriname National/International Trade - from reports/records 2005-2022**

202

203 Nearly 93% of Suriname's territory is covered by contiguous rain forest (FAO 2015) that extends
204 over the border with Brazil, French Guiana and Guyana. Suriname has numerous reports of
205 jaguar trade, which suggest high rates of removal of jaguars and reports of hunters selling jaguar
206 teeth in Paramaribo dating back to 2005 (Kernam 2010, World Animal Protection 2018,
207 Lemieux & Bruschi 2019, Verheij 2019). Several incidents support the assertion that the trade in
208 jaguar body parts in Suriname may be more pronounced than in neighboring countries.
209 According to CITES (2021), at least 60 jaguar teeth and a smaller number of other body parts
210 have been officially seized by the authorities from 2009 to 2020, 14 of which came from 3
211 seizures made at international airports, indicating international trafficking. According to news
212 and published reports on seizures, at least 11 jaguars were killed in Suriname between 2012 and
213 2018; three of the reports involved jaguar body parts claimed to be destined to China, comprising
214 two canines and four bodies or meat (Morcatty et al. 2020). Verheij (2019) estimated that at least
215 17 jaguars were killed between 2007 and January 2018 due to trafficking, and put an emphasis
216 on the involvement of both the Chinese diaspora and Chinese visitors in this trade. Trafficking
217 was apparent from the seizures of seven teeth in the Amsterdam airport in 2010 and 19 teeth in
218 the Paramaribo airport in 2018 (Verheij 2019) and 5 teeth also at Paramaribo airport in 2019
219 (Anonymous 2019). However, the intensity of the trade may be even higher. One informant
220 estimated over 80 jaguars killed in 2017 alone (Verheij 2019).

221

222 Following information from hunters and traders interviewed in 2009 that the main consumers of
223 jaguar parts were Chinese (Kerman 2010), subsequent research on the trade and trafficking of
224 jaguars in Suriname has focused largely on the Chinese communities living in Suriname, or on
225 Chinese nationals that visit the country (Lemieux & Bruschi 2019, Verheij 2019). Jaguar body
226 parts reportedly have diverse uses for Chinese people in Suriname, from medicinal application of
227 the meat and bones, especially skulls, to jewelry made from teeth (Kerman 2010). Earth League
228 International (2020) offered an online platform where wildlife trafficking information can be
229 anonymously reported. With regards to the trade in jaguars in Suriname, reports were received of
230 alleged killing and sale to Chinese buyers of jaguars from the Northwest Nickerie and
231 Wageningen region, as well as the area close to the international airport in the period 2017-2020.
232 Two Chinese-owned shops in the capital were singled out as selling jaguar parts, meat and jaguar
233 paste.

234

235 As early as 2010, records emerged of Chinese traffickers requesting suppliers for entire carcasses
236 for producing medicinal powder or paste (Kerman, 2010, Verheij 2019, Lemieux & Bruschi
237 2019). According to Verheij (2019), local informants also stated that teeth and processed
238 medicines were transported by passengers in flights to China as well as in timber containers
239 transported by ships. Jaguar teeth are used in necklaces and gold jewelry and thus bought and
240 sold in jewelry shops in Paramaribo (Kerman, 2010). An indirect factor elevating this trade is
241 that poorly patrolled new access roads to logging and gold mining sites have opened up
242 previously inaccessible forested regions, facilitating the establishment of trafficking routes.
243 Recent independent reports state that vendors actively approach villagers, loggers, gold miners
244 and hunters soliciting jaguar body parts (Lemieux & Bruschi, 2019, Verheij 2019). In March
245 2021, a baby jaguar was offered for sale on social media in Suriname with an asking price of
246 USD 2,500, and in October 2021 videos were posted on TikTok of a freshly killed jaguar; it was
247 unclear if this animal entered the trade.

248

249 We did not locate much evidence of online trade in Suriname in our study conducted May 2019-
250 March 2020, and found no posts advertising medicinal jaguar paste or powder. Verheij (2019)
251 reported several advertisements selling jaguar canines found on a Facebook group in Suriname
252 between 2016 and 2018, and 13 canines that resemble jaguar teeth posted on WeChat, an online
253 platform used by the Chinese community. Only 57.8% of Suriname’s population has access to
254 the internet. It is the country with the third lowest internet penetration in South America
255 (Miniwatts 2019), and thus online advertisements may not be a primary medium for the trade of
256 jaguar body parts, especially close to source areas.

257

258 **Peru National/International Trade - from reports/records 2014-2019**

259

260 The upper Amazon of Peru probably holds the second-largest jaguar population after Brazil
261 (Carrillo-Percastegui & Maffei 2016). In recent years, deforestation and gold mining in the
262 Amazon have aggravated the perils faced by jaguars (Swenson et al. 2011) as more people
263 penetrate previously inaccessible areas. Jaguars are sometimes killed due to livestock loss, a
264 pattern that is likely exacerbated as cattle ranching and small-scale agriculture expand (Tobler et
265 al. 2013). Both killing and trade seem to take place despite laws prohibiting killing of jaguars
266 and trade in their parts. Teeth, claws, and skin (whole or in parts) continue to be traded openly in
267 local markets across Peru, a situation that strongly indicates that more active, committed, and
268 courageous enforcement of existing laws is needed to change the situation.

269

270 Research on jaguar trade in the Peruvian Amazon carried out between October 2018 and January
271 2019 found 102 jaguar parts sold in 12 of the 19 localities studied, including Iquitos (Loreto),
272 Pucallpa (Ucayali), Puerto Maldonado (Madre de Dios) and Puno (Puno) (SERFOR & WCS
273 2020). Sales were most prevalent in the Amazon towns of Iquitos and Pucallpa, with a few teeth
274 found in Lima. A journalist, Berton (2018), researched jaguar trade in three markets in Iquitos
275 for seven days and found 44 canines, four skulls, five skins, and 70 claws. According to Berton
276 (2018), between 2000-2015 Peru’s National Forestry Service (also known by its Spanish
277 acronym ‘SERFOR’) seized 11 live jaguars and parts and products as 9 skulls, 14 skins, and 38
278 canines – the last product encountered in one confiscation event in March 2015. The implication
279 is that approximately the same amount of material was encountered by journalists in one week in
280 one city as the national authorities had confiscated in more than 30 incidents. If true, more

281 effective enforcement is needed. Based on official international seizures found in the UNODC
282 World Wise Database, Peru stands out as the most frequent source of jaguar body parts (CITES
283 2021). Brackowski et al. (2019) identified links between ‘ayahuasca’ tourism and jaguar related
284 trade, and that in tourism hubs jaguar body parts are openly sold on markets, with vendors
285 offering to help with export.
286

287 **Brazil National/International Trade in Jaguar Parts – from reports/records 2010-2019**

288
289 Brazil contains around 60% of the Amazonian rainforest and 66% of current jaguar range (de la
290 Torre et al. 2018). Although Brazil has been suggested as a potential source of wildlife for
291 international traffic (Phelps et al. 2010), little is known about the intensity of trade and the
292 impact of illegal wildlife trade on wild populations.

293 During online investigations, we recorded total of 42 unique online advertisements of jaguar
294 parts in Brazil in the last decade, involving 84 counted parts (72 teeth, 10 skins and two bodies)
295 (Polisar et al. 2023). Advertisements focused on handcrafts containing canines, such as
296 sculptures and necklaces, and skins, such as coats, carpets or wall decorations, potentially aimed
297 at a domestic market. Most of the online advertisements were encountered on online
298 marketplaces located through commonly used search engines or social media. However, seizure
299 reports and news indicate that there may be an existence of an international market for jaguar
300 body parts from Brazil (6.5% of the seizure reports) (Morcatty et al. 2020). This suggests that
301 stakeholders supplying international markets may use alternative methods to trade jaguar body
302 parts, other than advertising online or risking exposure in open fairs. Further research on that
303 matter is merited.
304

305 In an examination of reported seizures and news available online, the majority seemed to be
306 domestic trade in comparison to the international trade, accounting for near to 80% of the
307 individuals (46/57) and body parts seized (65/82) (Morcatty et al. 2020). Skulls represented 33%
308 of the seizures (27), followed by leather items 46.3% (38) and bodies 8% (6) (Morcatty et al.
309 2020). However, 56% of the skulls seized in recent years were directed to international markets.
310 Apart from skulls, all the remaining body parts seemed to supply the domestic market (Morcatty
311 et al. 2020). In 2016, 16 killed jaguars were seized in the countryside in Pará state by authorities
312 who raised strong concerns about links to wildlife trafficking. The official, though unpublished,
313 database of the Brazilian government reports ~ 50 infraction notices involving jaguars in Brazil,
314 however, most of those do not provide any details on the type of infraction (whether trade or
315 killing due to conflict with livestock) (unpublished data). Only four records explicitly stated that
316 pieces of skin and handcrafts were seized. The fine in one case was USD 2,400 (10,000 Brazilian
317 Real). In an investigation of open-air markets throughout the Brazilian Amazon and in South-
318 eastern Brazil conducted by members of our team in 2019, only a few pieces containing jaguar
319 skin or teeth in handcrafts were found. The sellers expressed fear of fines and prosecution due to
320 the illegality of the trade, confirming their awareness of the laws, but the persistence of material
321 offered in those venues suggest enforcement is ineffective.
322

323 In Brazil, selling an unauthorized piece of a native and protected species is a crime independent
324 of source, and the buyer may also receive the same penalties as the trader in case of proven
325 purchase. Simply liking or sharing a post advertising the trade of jaguar body parts, or
326 complimenting the piece that is for sale, is also breaking the law. The article 287 in the Penal

327 Code (Law n° 2.848/1940) states that public communication (apology or incitation) of a criminal
328 act is liable to punishment. Enforcement of all regulations across all scales, local, national, and
329 international is important. As a response, a Federal Task Force was formed in 2019 aiming
330 towards an integrated approach for counter-wildlife trafficking in Brazil.

331

332 **Current knowledge of status and trends in illegal trade in the remainder of South America**

333

334 Although detected in a much lesser degree, trade in jaguar parts exists in other South American
335 countries. During online investigations, we recorded posts offering visually-confirmed jaguar
336 parts linked to other countries, such as three posts in Venezuela and one in Uruguay (Polisar et
337 al. 2023). Additionally, seizure reports of illegally owned jaguar body parts included three cases
338 in Colombia, four in Paraguay, and one each in Ecuador and Venezuela in the last six years
339 (Morcatty et al. 2020).

340 Source South American countries with relatively high levels of corruption and Chinese private
341 investment and low income per capita had 10–50 times more jaguar seizures than the other
342 countries (Morcatty et al. 2020). Likewise, the links between jaguar trafficking, human-jaguar
343 conflict, and other criminal activities such as drug or weapons trafficking have been raised in
344 countries like Brazil and Guatemala (Arias et al. 2020, CITES, 2021). Regarding online trade,
345 internet penetration has proven to be a critical factor influencing online wildlife trade listings
346 (Nijman et al. 2023). the lower internet penetration combined with extent of jaguar range within
347 a country may be a factor leading to a low detection of online jaguar trade and seizure records.
348 The three countries adjacent to Brazil of Colombia, Venezuela, and Guyana have low internet
349 penetration (63.2%, 53% and 50.5%, respectively) yet individually and as a block contain a
350 considerable proportion of current jaguar range. Paraguay and Argentina have high internet
351 penetration (89.6% and 93.1%, respectively) but contain a relatively small proportion of total
352 jaguar range (Miniwatts 2019, de la Torre et al. 2018). The few online trade records we detected
353 for Suriname, compared to other reports emphasizing interviews and market searches (Kernam
354 2010, World Animal Protection 2018, Lemieux & Bruschi 2019, Verheij 2019) suggest a high
355 degree of variability in the role of online platforms in jaguar part commerce. This seems
356 potentially significant in the largely porous, remote, and unpatrolled common international
357 boundaries of Brazil, Guyana, Venezuela, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, and Bolivia, which have
358 likely low internet penetration. Increased physical vigilance by national and local authorities in
359 border areas is merited to prevent possible illegal trade threats from emerging in future.

360 In French Guiana records are maintained by the police division of a governmental agency titled
361 “Office Français de la Biodiversité” (French Biodiversity Office), that works mainly by checking
362 online social networks. The jaguar is not protected by a governmental decree (i.e., at the National
363 – French – level), but by a local decree, meaning that killing a jaguar is not a criminal offence,
364 but punished by a fine. Between 2018-2022 the division recorded one intentional killing), and
365 traffic of jaguar parts that involved one skin, 72 teeth (in seven different judiciary cases), and
366 eight claws.

367

368 **China and Vietnam**

369

370 In parts of Asia, Asian big cat parts and products are consumed for multiple purposes, including
371 skins for décor, taxidermy and non-financial bribes, teeth and claws for jewelry, and bones for
372 steeping in tonics, carving, and traditional medicine including ‘glue’ or ‘paste’ (EIA 2018).
373 Previous research has indicated China and Vietnam to be significant markets for tiger trade
374 (Gratwicke et al. 2008, Wildlife Justice Commission 2016, Wong 2016, Indenbaum 2018).

375
376 Verheij (2019) noted in Suriname, “there are indications that Chinese individuals were buying
377 jaguar parts as early as 2003”, and transnational trafficking has been generally viewed as an
378 emerging trend. Kerman (2010) noted for Suriname that jaguars were sold to Chinese nationals
379 as early as 2005. Aside from the seizures made in Bolivia and Suriname, which included Chinese
380 cities as destinations for jaguar body parts seized at post offices or airports, there are few
381 examples of confirmed seizures of jaguar body parts within Chinese territory. According to the
382 recent study on jaguar trade conducted by CITES (2021), China was identified as the destination
383 country in just three out of 76 (4%) jaguar seizures reported by UNODC’s World Wise Database
384 in the past two decades, involving less than 10 jaguar specimens (body parts or live animals;
385 CITES 2021). In that same study, internet searches yielded information on another three seizures
386 involving a total of 137 teeth (CITES 2021). Detections commonly feature teeth, and are
387 generally related to Chinese nationals either within Latin America or shipping into China
388 (Franco 2018, Kerman 2010, Leon 2018, Nuñez & Aliaga-Rossel 2016, Verheij 2019).

389
390 While many news articles have suggested that a wide variety of jaguar body parts (including
391 bones, meat, and organs) are being used in the context of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM)
392 in China, official seizure evidence is mostly limited to teeth, and there is scant official evidence
393 of the use of jaguar parts in TCM, making ‘Wenwan’ (subculture of collecting sophisticated
394 items) a more likely driver of the trade (Li et al. 2022). In China, news reports suggest two
395 pieces of alleged jaguar bones seized in 2014; 1,490 grams of jaguar bones and paws in 2014
396 (Anonymous 2014). The only official seizure made in China, referenced above, involved 119
397 jaguar teeth and 13 jaguar claws seized in 2015, the latter resulting in a custodial sentence of 4.5
398 years and a fine equivalent to USD 7,200 (He 2016). In 2019, nine ‘American lion’ teeth from
399 Peru were seized, later identified as puma (Verheij 2019). It is unclear if suspects arrested at
400 airports were in possession of jaguar parts for personal use, or intended to supply consolidators
401 in other jurisdictions. This has occurred against the backdrop of increasing trade in big cat teeth
402 in recent years, including on Asian online platforms (Indenbaum 2018). Despite the Suriname-
403 China links suggested by some reports, there is scant information from seizures within China
404 reflecting known links to Suriname.

405
406 Online research may be challenging as Chinese language does not clearly distinguish among
407 leopard, cheetah, clouded leopard, and jaguar, for example using the same character “豹” across
408 species. Chinese media also may confuse common names when reporting trade in big cats. The
409 Vietnamese language presents similar challenges for online research: online traders of big cats in
410 Vietnam refer to tigers and lions and products from these two species and all others big cats as
411 “báo”.

412
413 Jaguar parts featured in Chinese-language online posts cited “the Americas” as the source to
414 indicate jaguar parts, and both Chinese and Vietnamese platforms featured discussions about
415 how to differentiate the teeth of different big cats. Notably, genuine jaguar teeth were less likely

416 to occur in Vietnamese than Chinese posts; visual review of Vietnamese posts verified no images
417 of jaguar parts, however Chinese posts did contain jaguar teeth. We encourage and recommend
418 online research that includes additional countries in Asia.

419

420 **Legal considerations to control and eradicate jaguar trade in and from South America**

421

422 The killing of jaguars that eventually enter international trade are preventable at the local level,
423 within each country. National legal frameworks and their local implementation play an important
424 role in deterring opportunistic killings and accidental takes; they can also reduce the human-
425 carnivore conflict that may lead to killing jaguars, or to opportunistic trade of parts and products
426 in the underground market (Fukushima et al. 2021).

427

428 All jaguar range countries have entered the Convention on International Trade in Endangered
429 Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES). Jaguars are listed in Appendix I of CITES, which
430 prohibits commercial international trade of live animals, parts or products. According to this,
431 jaguar trade across South American borders is forbidden in the terms of the Convention, though
432 there is no similar homogenous framework for in-country legal provisions.

433

434 Other international instruments, such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the
435 Convention on the Conservation of the Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS), also
436 contribute to setting international standards for the maintenance of robust wildlife populations.
437 Implementation of international instruments relies solely on each country's development and
438 enforcement of their national and subnational – where applicable – legal frameworks.

439

440 Hunting and in-country trade laws, though not specifically covered in CITES, are oftentimes
441 contained in the same legal instruments approved to comply with said Convention. Such
442 instruments can contribute to curbing in-country trade, provided they include clauses to address
443 capacity-building and robust implementation among the local authorities. Importantly,
444 comparability of the legal frameworks in adjacent countries is needed as these instruments may
445 be applicable to jaguars (potentially, the same individuals) across borders.

446

447 Legal measures can be heightened when acknowledging that consequences extend beyond
448 conservation issues, impacting economic, health, and security ramifications associated with
449 illegal activities (Cardoso et al. 2021). A range-wide review of national legal frameworks within
450 countries in the jaguar range by Kretser et al. (2022) offers insights on the legal trends informing
451 national laws and suggests legal best practices and ways to strengthen existing laws related to
452 trade of jaguar parts. Recently, the enactment of Law N° 1525 for the Protection and
453 Conservation of the Andean Condor, Kuntur Mallku (*Vultur gryphus*) in Bolivia, included an
454 additional provision that categorizes illegal wildlife trafficking as a criminal offense within the
455 Penal Code of Bolivia.

456 How countries design and enforce administrative and criminal penalties has far-reaching
457 implications for jaguar conservation, especially in areas where subsistence hunting takes place,
458 and where human-wildlife conflict is escalating. Administrative penalties are applied to
459 infractions of regulations and may be enforceable by countries' wildlife authorities; criminal
460 penalties are enacted by criminal courts. Penalties (and the probability of them being enforced)
461 need to be high enough to deter opportunistic killings, not only among the local population but

462 most importantly to middlemen that have access to international underground markets. All South
463 American countries include both administrative and criminal penalties for illegal killing of
464 endangered species, such as jaguars. However, many of the penalties are calculated based on
465 each country's minimum wage (Ecuador, Peru, Colombia) and might be insufficient to deter
466 hunters that supply trade for the international market.

467
468 All countries require hunting licenses for sport hunting of wildlife, but not all require licenses for
469 subsistence hunting, and many allow for killings under the umbrella of self-defense (Kretser et
470 al. 2022). Hunting licenses are granted by local or national officers in the executive branch –
471 often times a regional manager, or a national-level directorate – and while it is unlikely that a
472 public official would grant a permit to hunt jaguars, some of the existing frameworks have not
473 made it entirely illegal.

474
475 The legality of jaguar killings is delicate, as only Paraguay and Argentina have national level
476 laws that place the species in a special category, and it would require Congress to pass a new law
477 in order to lift the protections. In contrast, the majority of South American countries (except
478 Bolivia, French Guiana and Suriname), place jaguars in a special management category by
479 listing them alongside all the endangered species in the country. While such lists are potentially
480 efficient management strategies, they present certain weaknesses: they often rely on the global
481 conservation status of the species, rather than the national status, and they are typically infra-
482 legal level regulations; that is, vulnerable to being modified by a low-level executive order.

483
484 Most countries allow for subsistence hunting, particularly for Indigenous Peoples and/or local
485 communities. Each country's enforcement determines whether wildlife parts and by-products can
486 be traded after allegedly hunting for subsistence reasons. Local non-monetary trade of meat and
487 animal by-products within rural communities is quite common. However, subsistence hunting of
488 game species for food should not enter commercial trade. Market hunting to satisfy urban
489 demands for cash returns is usually detrimental to game populations (Robinson & Bennett 2000,
490 Greenberg 2014) and presumably, also to the jaguars that depend on those prey species (Polisar
491 et al. 2003, Novack 2005, Foster et al. 2014, McNab et al. 2019). For jaguar conservation, the
492 case is clear; no commercial trade of jaguar parts should be legal. Allowing any trade in jaguar
493 parts leaves a door open for abuse, fraudulent interpretation of the law and the potential rapid
494 decline of jaguar populations.

495
496 For human-wildlife conflict where some flexibility to address chronic losses exists, few laws
497 ensure such flexibility is not abused, since it potentially provides a window to legitimize killing
498 for trade. To stop wildlife parts and by-products originated from legal self-defense or
499 depredation control killings from entering the market – and therefore creating an incentive to
500 cover up illegal hunting for trade – countries could adopt provisions similar to Peru: where the
501 forest authority is in charge of disposing of the remains of legally-killed jaguars (with prior
502 governmental authorization). While enforcement is not yet ideal in Peru, such a legal mandate
503 would simplify authorities' efforts to confiscate dead jaguars, thereby preventing parts from
504 entering illegal trade.

505
506 Given the complexity of these issues only a combination of policies, deterrence mechanisms and
507 reinforced implementation efforts have a chance at stopping illegal trade (Fukushima et al.

2021). Since legislation in each country already regulates against trafficking in the parts of threatened and endangered species, including jaguar, the primary need is to enforce existing laws more actively and effectively in both rural areas where the killing happens and urban areas where demand for parts may exist. At the same time, given that a considerable proportion of jaguar killings are associated with opportunistic encounters between humans and jaguars, human-jaguar conflict, and subsistence/cultural practices, it is essential to include behavior change, awareness building, and alternative livelihoods efforts into the mix of interventions to deter jaguar trafficking (Arias et al. 2021a). Finally, tech companies must bear responsibility for illicit transactions on their platforms, as they play a role in facilitating illegal wildlife trade (Morcatty et al. 2022), including transactions involving jaguars.

518

519 **Discussion and Conclusions**

520

521 Recent questions regarding trade in jaguar parts have included: 1) is the extent of Asia driven
522 trade in jaguar parts, especially teeth, echoed in additional countries but thus far poorly detected?
523 2) what are the relative proportions of domestic and international commerce? 3) what needs to be
524 done to halt the trade? In this review we found: 1) widespread evidence of domestic commerce in
525 several countries, mostly unimpeded by law enforcement; 2) a narrower band of evidence of
526 international transport of jaguar parts (which by definition are collected on local and national
527 levels before export), including to Asia. Teeth were the most common part traded. All South
528 American countries in the jaguar range have some evidence of jaguar trade, but international
529 trade is particularly concerning in Bolivia, Peru, Suriname and Brazil due to potentially higher
530 volumes; 3) ambiguity as to how much domestic trade enters international trade.

531 The number of interceptions of jaguar parts in China has been low but concerning nevertheless
532 due to the amount of body parts traded, and seizures in South America with direct links to China,
533 which indicate that jaguar body parts may have entered that country without being seized. Online
534 searches revealed jaguar parts on Chinese platforms and advertised in Chinese, yet in low
535 numbers. Thus far, online and interception records of material coming from Suriname and other
536 potential source countries in South America to China do not match the volume implied in some
537 published reports focused on source countries. Two conclusions may be drawn: 1) trade in jaguar
538 parts may be coming into China from several sources in South America, but has been difficult to
539 detect, record and disrupt; 2) while not diminishing the gravity of existing and potential South
540 America to Asia trade in jaguar parts, currently domestic commerce in jaguar parts in source
541 countries may vastly exceed international commerce. Conclusion 2 emphasizes the dramatic
542 need for improved national level education and enforcement within South America to curb all
543 commerce in jaguar parts. Both conclusions (1 & 2) represent grave threats. More investigative
544 efforts are needed to examine jaguar trafficking from South America to Asia, and wherever
545 encountered, disrupt it. Given international travel between the two regions, and the frequency of
546 legitimate commercial shipments that provide opportunities to smuggle wildlife parts, increased
547 vigilance and additional investigations are recommended.

548

549 While it remains necessary to investigate the illegal trade in jaguars in China, the growing
550 evidence of international trade in jaguar body parts points towards a wider geographical scope.
551 In particular, some North American and European countries, including the United States,
552 Mexico, Germany and France have been found to have some of the highest numbers of official
553 jaguar seizures (CITES 2021). These markets have received less attention than China, and they

554 are not well understood in terms of their drivers or scale. Several jaguar seizure events in range
555 countries have taken place in touristic areas frequented by foreign and national tourists,
556 suggesting that tourism may be an underestimated driver of jaguar trade (Brackowski et al.
557 2019, Arias et al. 2020, CITES 2021).

558
559 Using online searches, we identified records that law enforcement could review for actionable
560 information, and recommend additional online research in future to locate illegal trade to curb
561 the threats to wild jaguar populations. Comparing the preliminary results of our online searches
562 to other sources (Kerman 2010, Lemiex & Bruschi 2019, Verheij 2019, SERFOR & WCS 2020,
563 World Animal Protection 2018) and team member experiences in the upper and lower Amazon,
564 we note that even when sampling bias is avoided in online searches, variation in consistent
565 electricity/internet across regions and trading contexts preferred among vendors means that
566 online searches should be complemented by on-the-ground market reconnaissance and searches
567 by mandated agencies. The greater Amazon includes nine of eighteen jaguar range states; the
568 scale of the forest and porous international boundaries suggest that more research is advisable
569 and greater vigilance and enforcement even in the more remote areas will be very important.

570 Recognizing the international nature of the trade in jaguars, since November 2021 Suriname has
571 deployed two specifically-trained jaguar detecting dogs at the international airport and other
572 border posts. Increased enforcement in domestic commerce in Peru seems a priority. However,
573 seizures without prosecution may elevate killing to replace stock lost. Tackling markets at all
574 levels will require improvements in enforcement, surveillance efforts tracking different
575 transportation routes, as well as improvement of capabilities and commitments to investigate and
576 effectively prosecute wildlife poaching and trafficking cases.

577 The prevalence of jaguar parts in trade that we encountered, some of which may have originated
578 in lethal responses to human-jaguar conflict, illustrates the importance of more effectively
579 regulating local and national trade, so there are no disincentives to finesse coexistence due to a
580 market that motivates killing jaguars for profit (Reuter et al. 2018). We also recommend greater
581 efforts at effective outreach and investment that elevate the uptake of non-lethal conflict
582 mitigation, as well as economic alternatives integrated with conservation that generate incentives
583 to maintain live wild jaguars and intact natural wildlife communities.

584 A key issue that we identified, and which has also been raised by other attempts to collate and
585 systematize information on jaguar trade (e.g., CITES 2021), was the lack of a centralized and
586 reliable information on the matter. Reports of jaguar trade come from diverse sources varying in
587 their quality and verification status, while data on official seizures made by enforcement
588 authorities may be missing or unpublished. This has challenged the separation of facts from
589 anecdotal information, and has presented challenges in evaluating the actual scale and trends of
590 jaguar trade. The recommendations generated during the meeting of the jaguar range states in
591 Cuiaba, Brazil, 18-22 September 2023 offer cause for optimism. Greater international
592 collaboration to combat illegal cross-border trade is one of seven themes to be considered in a
593 continental jaguar action plan. In addition, the CITES Standing Committee has requested that the
594 Secretariat prepare terms of reference for the creation of modular system for monitoring illegal
595 killing of jaguars and illegal trade in their parts and derivatives, which provides an opportunity to
596 improve our capacity to evaluate the trade, and disrupt it (CITES 2023a, CITES 2023b).

597 Almost all sampling includes some form of bias. Seizure data may be biased towards countries

598 with greater enforcement capacity and reporting practices. Online searches may be biased
599 towards areas with better electricity and internet accessibility. In this regard, there is a great
600 value to proactive and carefully designed investigations that intentionally reduce bias (Arias
601 2020, Arias 2021a, Arias 2021b, Morcatty et al. 2020, Earth League International 2021) to
602 support conservation. Cooperation between independent and academic researchers and national
603 authorities, that include collaborative “methods and information transfers” can elevate
604 knowledge and enable the interceptions that are important to disrupt the trade. Our
605 recommendations are strengthened monitoring of physical and online markets to identify threats,
606 supported by mandated law enforcement using existing mechanisms to disrupt trade in jaguar
607 parts at all levels, local, national and international, whilst exploring multi-faceted approaches
608 that do not criminalize vulnerable communities. Law enforcement should be complemented by
609 social awareness, behavior change and alternative livelihood programs that reduce the incentives
610 to poach and trade jaguars.

611

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822 Hat, Damian Rumiz, Museo Historia Natural Noel Kempff

823 Skin (hide) Omar Torrico, WCS Bolivia

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